

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Predicting Electromagnetic Field Exposure Using Artificial Intelligence Methods

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ABSTRACT This study explores the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in predicting electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure levels in urban environments. Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models were developed to estimate the electric field (E, in V/m) at specific locations without requiring direct measurements. Measurements were conducted in Thessaloniki, Greece, covering a diverse urban landscape, including commercial and residential areas. The methodology involved collecting EMF data using high-precision equipment, validating and refining publicly available datasets, and extracting key features using Geographic Information System (GIS) tools. Essential input features included distances to the nearest base stations, their installation heights, classification of base stations regarding their emitted power, number of obstructing buildings, built area density, and line-of-sight (LOS) conditions. The AI models demonstrated strong predictive performance, with mean absolute errors (MAE) slightly above 0.3 V/m. The study highlights the importance of proper data preprocessing, feature selection, and integration of real-world measurements into AI-based prediction models. The results suggest that AI can serve as a reliable alternative for EMF exposure assessment, potentially reducing the need for costly and time-consuming field measurements while ensuring compliance with safety regulations.

INDEX TERMS Electromagnetic field (EMF) prediction, artificial intelligence (AI), deep learning (DL), machine learning (ML), radiofrequency electromagnetic fields (RF-EMF), base station (BS) antennas.

I. INTRODUCTION

The public concern about the potential health effects resulting from the exposure to electromagnetic fields (EMFs) is a persistent phenomenon. The continuous evolution of telecommunications and wireless technologies, and the introduction of new systems like 5G cellular networks intensify these worries. EMF measurements for assessing compliance with regulatory limits [1] are elaborate and time-consuming tasks that require trained personnel, expensive equipment, and a significant time investment. Assessing the electric field without direct measurements is challenging

despite the existence of numerous radio propagation models. These models typically consider specific conditions like line-of-sight and reflections from particular surfaces, but real-world environments exhibit unique characteristics with high variability. Accurately simulating the electric field in a specific area requires substantial effort to construct an environment using specialized software and running simulations. An alternative approach to this problem involves employing Machine Learning (ML) or Deep Learning (DL) algorithms. This necessitates identifying the feature variables (or 'features') that influence the electric field (E-field), collecting relevant data, and performing a significant number of measurements of the E-field values, which serve as the target variables, aiming to predict them.

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This work aims:

- a. To identify the feature variables needed for accurate prediction of electric field outdoors in an urban environment where the downlink electric field of cellular networks dominates but measurements are not available.
- b. To demonstrate effective methods for gathering representative data for feature variables that are not readily available to collect or assess, such as the built environment around a spot measurement of the electric field.
- c. To emphasize the significance of data cleaning in an implementation using ML and DL models to predict electric fields.
- d. To discuss how the availability of additional data could further improve the prediction accuracy of AI models.

II. EMPIRICAL OUTDOOR RADIO PROPAGATION MODELS

Studying the Friis equation for free space and propagation models [2], especially those applicable to urban environments like Okumura et al. [3], helps in identifying some key features essential for predicting the electric field at a specific location.

The Friis equation for free space calculates the power received at a point from a transmitting antenna in free space conditions, where the path loss L_F is

$$L_F = \left(\frac{4\pi d}{\lambda} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

with d the distance between the transmission and reception antennas, and λ the wavelength. However, in an urban environment, free space conditions do not exist due to the presence of structures such as buildings, parked or moving cars, and vegetation between the transmitting and receiving antennas. The propagation mechanisms cause fading of the electromagnetic waves and time delay spread, resulting in random multipath phenomena inside an urban environment.

The Okumura model is a widely used empirical model for predicting radio propagation in urban environments, developed by Yoshihisa Okumura in the 1960's [3]. The model is based on extensive measurements taken in various environments in Japan, and it has been adapted for use in other parts of the world. It estimates the median path loss L_{50} by combining the free-space path loss L_F , median attenuation $A_{mu}(f,d)$ and the correction factor $G(h_{te})$ and $G(h_{re})$ for height gain of the transmitting and receiving antenna, respectively. The basic equation is

$$L_{50} \text{ (dB)} = L_F + A_{mu}(f, d) - G(h_{te}) - G(h_{re}) - G_{AREA} \quad (2)$$

where f is the frequency and d is again the distance. The term $A_{mu}(f,d)$ represents the median attenuation factor relative to free space, accounting for additional losses due to terrain, buildings, and environmental conditions [3]. These attenuation values are empirically derived from measurements and vary based on frequency and distance, with different attenuation curves used to represent propagation conditions for various frequency ranges and transmitter-receiver distances. The term G_{AREA} is the area correction factor,

which accounts for variations in propagation conditions across different environments, such as dense urban, suburban, and rural areas [3]. The Okumura model provides power prediction plots for frequency bands at 150 MHz, 450 MHz, 900 MHz, and 1500 MHz. However, it is typically extended to cover frequencies up to 3 GHz. The model is applicable for distances ranging from 1 to 100 km and for antenna heights ranging from 30 m to 100 m —values that align with those observed in our study involving Base Station Antennas (BSA). The COST 231 Walfisch-Ikegami [4] model excels in scenarios where the dominant propagation mechanism is over the rooftop, making it suitable for transmitters above the average rooftop level. This model considers the effects of buildings and streets, providing a detailed approach to urban signal attenuation. The path loss L is calculated using the formula

$$L = L_{bf} + L_{rts} + L_{msdL} \quad (3)$$

where L_{bf} is the free-space path loss, L_{rts} accounts for rooftop-to-street diffraction and scatter, and L_{msdL} considers multi-screen diffraction loss. Key features in this model include the height of buildings, street width, building separation, and antennas heights. The model differentiates between line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) scenarios. For LOS situations, where the Base Station (BS) and mobile antenna are within a street canyon, a specific propagation loss formula is used, which differs from the standard free space loss equation.

All radio propagation models (including free space) offer insights into how variables such as distance, frequency, and environmental factors (e.g., urban density and building heights) affect the electric field received at a specific point. Moreover, LOS and NLOS conditions, antenna heights, and terrain obstructions are critical for accurate field estimation. This exploration of empirical radio propagation models can assist with feature variable selection for the developed AI predictive models.

III. RELATED WORKS

The available research on predicting spatial EMF exposure levels using AI is limited, with studies focusing on either indoor or outdoor environments. These studies rely on real measurements or synthetic data, and each examines different frequencies based on the environment or use case. Neskovic et al. [5] developed a model for predicting indoor electric field strength in mobile environments using a feedforward Artificial Neural Network (ANN) at the 900 MHz frequency band. This model was based on extensive field measurements collected from two university buildings and achieved a root mean square error (RMSE) of 3.6 dB. The work by Tognola et al. [6] presents a ML approach using ANN models to estimate radiofrequency (RF) exposure in indoor environments, specifically focusing on WiFi sources at 2.4 GHz in scenarios involving both downlink and uplink transmissions. The models achieved an RMSE of 2.5 to 5.1 dB across different exposure conditions.

Mazloum et al. [7] focused on UL power prediction in 4G networks using real measurements from a six-floor residential building. Their model, based on a feedforward artificial neural network, achieved a MAE of 1.487 dB, demonstrating a strong correlation between UL power, floor level, and time. Liu et al. [8] introduced a graph neural networks (GNN) based model to predict EMF distribution in indoor environments using data from a ray-tracing simulator at 28 GHz. The model incorporated factors like geometry, material properties, and transmitter positions, achieving an MAE of 4.043 dB, particularly excelling in line-of-sight regions. The work by Bilson et al. [9] used a physics-informed machine learning approach to model RF-EMF exposure in 5G Massive MIMO systems, incorporating physical laws like the Friis transmission equation into a gradient-boosted ensemble of decision trees. Based on both indoor and outdoor measurements collected at the University of Surrey, the model achieved an R^2 of 0.86. In outdoor environments Neskovic and Neskovic [10] developed a model for predicting electric field strength in urban microcell environments using real-world measurements at 900 MHz, with an RMSE of 4.85 dB. Fraiha et al. [11] modeled electric field strength near transmitter towers at 600 MHz using a hybrid ARIMA and neural network approach. Their model improved prediction accuracy by 65% compared to traditional methods, demonstrating its effectiveness for assessing non-ionizing radiation exposure. Wang et al. [12] predicted spatial EMF exposure using a hybrid ANN model, which achieved optimal performance when incorporating data from neighboring base stations. The model was trained on data collected through drive test measurements across a wide frequency range from 700 to 2700 MHz and utilized a sliding window method to smooth out the variations during prediction. Wang and Wiart [13] employed a hybrid ANN model that combined sensor networks and public base station data to predict EMF exposure with high accuracy, even in noisy urban settings. The data were collected through drive tests and continuous sensor measurements, processed using methods similar to moving averages to smooth variations. The work by Mallik et al. [14] focused on reconstructing EMF exposure maps in urban environments using sparse sensor data and a Convolutional Neural Tangent Kernel (CNTK) approach, addressing the challenge of accurately reconstructing exposure maps with limited data. The paper by Chikha et al. [15] used a moving average method over a sliding window to smooth out noise and random fluctuations in the electric field (E-field) measurements collected during drive tests in Paris. The measurements, taken with a real-time spectrum analyzer and a 3-axis probe mounted on a vehicle, spanned a frequency range from 700 MHz to 3800 MHz, covering multiple cellular bands (2G, 3G, 4G, and 5G), providing the input data for their ANN model.

More extensive research has been conducted on path loss estimation for radio propagation using AI, with models like the one by Jo et al. [16] leveraging real-world data from suburban environments. Their approach, combining

principle component analysis (PCA), ANN, and Gaussian Processes, demonstrated superior accuracy over traditional models. Sotiroudis et al. [17], [18] used synthetic data to estimate path loss in urban settings, applying AI models to achieve accurate results.

To our knowledge, this is the first work attempting to predict electric field levels at specific spots in an urban environment across multiple frequencies.

IV. METHODS

An AI predictive model aims to estimate continuous electric field values without requiring direct measurements. To achieve this, it is essential to collect both the target variable measurements and the relevant feature variables on which these measurements depend. For each measurement, numerous features are collected to aid with prediction. In this section we present the measurement equipment and methodology for measuring the electric field (target variable), the area where the measurements were performed, the essential features influencing our target variable, the feature variables data we collected, and the sources used for extracting them. Based on the reviewed literature in Section III, which highlights the main factors affecting EMF levels, the design of our measurement campaign and feature selection strategy was informed by established propagation modeling principles and recent AI-based studies.

A. MEASUREMENT EQUIPMENT AND PROCEDURE

The measurements were conducted using the SRM-3006 basic unit from Narda Safety Test Solutions (Pfullingen, Germany). The SRM-3006, which has a wide frequency range from 9 kHz to 6 GHz, was directly connected to two isotropic tri-axial E-field antennas, also provided by Narda Safety Test Solutions. The antennas have different frequencies (27 MHz to 3 GHz and 420 MHz to 6 GHz) and dynamic measurement ranges (0.2 mV/m to 200 V/m and 0.14 mV/m to 160 V/m, respectively). Two service tables were generated. The first table covered frequencies from 27 MHz to 3 GHz using the first antenna, while the second table covered frequencies from 3 GHz to 6 GHz using the second antenna. The SRM-3006 was configured in “Safety Evaluation” mode, with the resolution bandwidth (RBW) set to the automatic option recommended by the manufacturer. According to this setting, the RBW is determined using the equation:

$$\text{RBW} \leq \frac{F_{\text{span}} (\text{narrowest service})}{4} \quad (4)$$

The device then selects the next smaller available RBW value, which varies depending on the span of each frequency band. [19].

At each measurement spot, measurements were performed at three different heights, 110 cm, 150 cm, and 170 cm - following the guidelines outlined in IEC 62232 [20]. Results were obtained using the average trace over time, with each measurement lasting 2 minutes at each height. The

electric field value at each height i and frequency band f that corresponds to the selected assigned service was stored. The electric field for each frequency band f was determined from the data collected at three different heights at the measurement location as

$$E_f = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 E_{i,f}^2}{3}} \quad (5)$$

The total electric field value for that specific spot was then calculated as

$$E = \sqrt{\sum_f E_f^2} \quad (6)$$

It is noted that the target variable represents the total electric field values derived solely from cellular frequencies, excluding contributions from other frequency bands or services, like broadcasting.

All measurements were conducted on weekdays, within standard business hours. Mobile devices used by equipment operators were switched off or set to airplane mode to prevent the creation of downlink traffic that could cause beamforming towards the measurement location and increase the BS's output power. Mobile devices of pedestrians could not be controlled, but did not affect measurements due to the following reasons: (1) Pedestrians usually take their distance from the measurement equipment, when they realize a measurement is taking place. (2) At each height the measurement is a 2-minute average, therefore any random variation of the field caused by nearby mobile devices activity is effectively averaged out. This setup was chosen specifically to measure the exposure levels of the general public at ground-level locations that are open to the public, like squares and parks, or heavily frequented areas by the public, like transportation stations.

The measurements took place in the municipality of Thessaloniki, covering an area of approximately 7 km² and including several points of interest (POIs) such as parks, bus stops, university campuses, and shopping centers, which are areas attracting large numbers of visitors. The population density in the municipality of Thessaloniki is approximately 16,530 residents/km² (2021). The density of cellular BS antennas is approximately 55 BS/km². A grid of measurement points was established for this area, considering the locations of POIs. This resulted in a grid with 149 ground-level measurement points (Fig. 1). It is worth noting that the measurements include both the commercial center of Thessaloniki, which has many shops, malls, tourist spots, and parks, as well as an area, which includes almost entirely residences. Our aim was to ensure that the selected area did not represent just a specific profile, as we want the selected feature variables to be able to predict EMF in any urban environment.

B. TARGET VARIABLE DATASET

The aim of this study was to develop a method for estimating EMF exposure caused by the downlink transmission link in

cellular networks. To achieve this, we measured the electric field values exclusively within cellular bands. Initially, we used 99 measurements as target variable values to construct the first AI models. These measurements were performed between May 2023 and July 2023. However, the performance metrics of the AI models constructed with this first dataset were poor, because the models could not make accurate predictions for values >1.5 V/m. This issue was attributed to the small number of high-value electric field measurements included in this initial dataset. To address this limitation, we conducted 50 additional measurements in April 2024 in areas with higher electric field values, resulting in an augmented dataset of 149 target variable values (Fig. 1). Fig. 2 shows the number of instances of the measured electric field at the spots of the initial and the augmented datasets.

FIGURE 1. Spot measurements in the selected area and the location of the base stations. The blue asterisks indicate the locations where broadband monitoring sensors have been installed in the same area.

C. FEATURE VARIABLES

Following the discussion on the existing propagation models (empirical and AI), the first column of Table 1 summarizes the identified features which influence the measured electric field (target variable). We did not include in this column any features of the receiving antenna and measuring unit, as we used calibrated equipment, which is capable of directly providing the electric field value for different frequencies.

D. COLLECTING AND CLEANING DATA ON FEATURE VARIABLES

1) DATA SOURCES AND SOFTWARE

Perhaps the most important and time-consuming part of developing an AI predictive model is finding and collecting the appropriate data on the feature variables that contribute towards accurate predictions. It is crucial that the feature data are as free of inconsistencies and errors as possible. In Greece, locations, heights, and some technical

TABLE 1. Essential and collected features with their sources for retrieval or estimation.

Key features (deriving from propagation models)	Used features corresponding to key features (based on availability)	Names of used features (and their Corresponding Values)	Source of information
Horizontal Distance to BSs	Calculation of Horizontal Distances to the 12 Nearest BSs	Distance x (in meters), where $x=1,2,\dots,12$	EETT / OSM / QGIS
Height of BSs	Installation Heights of the 12 Nearest BSs	Height x (in meters), where $x=1,2,\dots,12$	EETT
Transmitting Antenna Power and Gain (Pt, Gt)	Macrocell or Microcell Classification for the 12 Nearest BSs	Macrocell x , where $x=1,2,\dots,12$ (1 = Macrocell, 0 = Microcell)	EETT
LOS/NLOS, Intersecting Buildings	Number of Intersecting Buildings Between Measurement Spot and Each of the 12 Nearest BSs	Intersect x , where $x=1,2,\dots,12$ (Number of intersecting buildings, with 0=LOS condition)	OSM, QGIS
Built area around the measurement spot	Average Distance to the 10 Nearest Buildings & Built Area within a 50 m Radius Buffer Around Each Spot	AVG Dist 10 Build (Average Distance in Meters) & Buffer Area (Built Area in m ²)	OSM, QGIS
Antenna Azimuth, Tilt, and HPBW (LOS Conditions)	Number of Antenna Sectors from the 3 Closest BSs with LOS (where Intersect x = 0)	SectorCoverageFlag x , where $x=1,2,3$ (Number of sectors illuminating the spot)	QGIS, On site considerations

FIGURE 2. Number of instances of electric field values (E in V/m) in the initial and augmented datasets.

characteristics of Base Stations (BSs) are publicly available on the website of EETT (Hellenic Telecommunications and Post Commission) [21]. Additionally, data were extracted from databases stored in OpenStreetMap (OSM) [22], often used in conjunction with QGIS software [23]. Moreover, as part of the data preparation process, we applied several domain-specific feature engineering techniques to enhance model performance. These included: (i) encoding categorical variables such as Macrocell/Microcell classification; (ii) standardizing numerical inputs using StandardScaler; and (iii) constructing meaningful features like the SectorCoverageFlag (based on LOS and HPBW), the number of intersecting buildings, the built area within a n-meter buffer, and the average distance to the n-closest buildings. These features were deliberately designed to reflect physical parameters known to influence EMF propagation, based on both theoretical propagation models and empirical knowledge.

Next, we discuss in more detail the data we collected on features, how we checked them for errors, and the alternative methods we used to estimate essential data when they were not readily available.

2) DISTANCE TO BASE STATIONS AND INSTALLATION HEIGHT OF BASE STATIONS

A key factor influencing the electric field value at each measurement point is the distance to the nearest BSs. There are two methods for incorporating this distance as a feature in an AI model: using the raw coordinates of the measurement locations and BSs, or using the calculated horizontal distance between them. We opted for the second method, as it is more generalizable and can be applied to areas outside the selected region.

At each measurement spot, we recorded the coordinates of the measurements. The locations of the BSs were extracted from publicly available data on the EETT website [21]. They were further verified or corrected, using recent photos from Google Street View. In some cases where the BSs were not visible due to outdated photos or other obstructions, we conducted site visits to record the locations with high accuracy. Both the measurement and BS coordinates were loaded into QGIS software to find the horizontal distances.

For each spot measurement, we determined the distances from the twelve closest BSs. We found that after considering 12 BSs, the models did not improve their performance further. Specifically, using the ExtraTrees Regressor machine learning algorithm (see Section V. Results), we trained the model with features derived from the 4 to 13 closest BSs

and evaluated the MAE on the test dataset. In each case, the model was fed with the full set of extracted features, while only the distance-related inputs corresponding to the n closest BSs were adjusted. The MAE values ranged from 0.3461V/m down to 0.3125V/m, with the lowest error observed when the model incorporated information from the 12 closest BSs. Notably, when considering 9 or more BSs, the MAE consistently remained below 0.32V/m. Although the number 12 might sound large, in Greece, it is common to have BSs from all three cellular providers on the same rooftop. The number of BSs to be considered is further supported by related studies in the literature: Chikha et al. [15] used distances from the 16 closest base stations, while Wang and Wiart [13] considered the 10 nearest BSs in their modeling approach.

The installation heights of the BSs were retrieved from the EETT database and validated through the photographs or during the in-situ visit.

3) TRANSMITTED POWER

The EETT database should also include records for antenna power and gain, but many of these values were missing. However, excluding the corresponding BSs due to the lack of data would not have been appropriate. Instead, we employed an alternative approach for assessing the transmitted power. In Greece, there are two types of cellular BSs: macrocell antennas (MAs), typically installed on rooftops in urban environments, and small cell antennas (SCAs), usually installed at lower heights. SCAs are subject to a simpler licensing regime but are restricted to a total effective isotropic radiated power not exceeding 164 W EIRP. MAs generally have higher power levels than SCAs. The EETT website [21] accurately records whether a BS is an MA or an SCA. Consequently, rather than using the actual power values of the BSs, we utilized the classification of each BS as either an MA or an SCA as an input feature for our models.

4) LOS AND NLOS

We used QGIS software to analyze the locations of measurements and BSs, determining the number of intersecting buildings between them (Fig. 3a). The building layer, showing all buildings in the area of interest, was sourced from the corresponding OSM layer. If the number of intersecting buildings is zero, it indicates LOS conditions. Additionally, we made manual corrections because some intersecting buildings were of low height compared to the BS, resulting in cases where there were LOS conditions despite one or more intersecting buildings. This manual adjustment was necessary due to the lack of building height information for Thessaloniki. If building height information is available, the above procedure can be fully automated for determining LOS/NLOS conditions.

The number of intersecting buildings between the measuring spots and BSs was used as a feature in the models. In cases of LOS conditions, we further assessed the ‘‘SectorCoverageFlag’’ feature, which is discussed in the

next ‘Measurement points coverage analysis’ paragraph. This feature addresses the possibility that, although LOS conditions exist, the antenna’s orientation might or might not be towards the spot, placing the spot inside or outside the antenna’s main lobe.

FIGURE 3. a) Distance between measuring spot (red dot) and the 12 closest BSs (black dots). The yellow blocks indicate the intersected buildings between them. b) On site consideration for assessing the feature ‘‘SectorCoverageFlag’’. c) A 50m radius buffer around the spot (green circle) with the buildings (blue) inside the buffer, whose area was calculated. d) The distances between a spot and the 20 closest buildings.

5) MEASUREMENT POINTS COVERAGE ANALYSIS

An important feature that critically affects the electric field at a specific spot is whether the spot is simply in the boresight of the transmitting antenna or within its Half-Power Beamwidth (HPBW) in both the horizontal and vertical planes. The features that can be utilized in this context are the azimuth of the antenna (horizontal plane), the corresponding elevation angle (vertical plane), the tilt, and the HPBW in both planes. Of course, the most accurate information in this context can come from the radiation pattern of the antennas, but this approach is rather time-consuming for many measurements. In our study, the publicly available data lacks accurate information for the azimuth, elevation, tilt angle, and HPBW of the BSAs. Instead of attempting to impute this missing data, we took a different approach by manually collecting the relevant information. This step is combined with the previous one, as it was done only for LOS conditions. Thus, we created a feature named ‘SectorCoverageFlag,’ which indicates, for

each spot, the number of sector antennas from the n -closest BSs whose HPBW includes the measurement spot. The ‘SectorCoverageFlag’ feature was assessed separately for each of the n -closest LOS BSs. For example, if a spot was within the HPBW of two sectors from a given BS, the ‘SectorCoverageFlag’ value for that BS was set to two. If the measurement spot was within the LOS conditions at a significant distance from the BS, resulting in a wide angle outside the HPBW of the sectors, the ‘SectorCoverageFlag’ feature was assigned a value of zero. Regarding the HPBW of the antennas we retrieved the data from the EETT website. When the information about the HPBW was missing, the ‘SectorCoverageFlag’ was set to 1 if the measurement spot was within $\pm 45^\circ$ in the horizontal plane and within 30° downward in the vertical plane (with 0 degrees being a vector perpendicular to the surface of the antenna or “sector”). From several records of BSA on the EETT website, the HPBW for the horizontal plane was typically within 30° - 90° . For the vertical plane, the corresponding angles were smaller, typically 5° - 30° . Fig. 3b demonstrates a measurement near an SCA BS including two antennas (two sectors). Feature ‘SectorCoverageFlag’ for that BS was set to the value of one, because the measurement spot is within the HPBW angles for both planes only for Sector 1. Sector 2 views the spot at an angle larger than 90° , i.e., the spot lies outside the HPBW of the antenna in the horizontal plane; thus, Sector 2 was not considered for the ‘SectorCoverageFlag’ feature. This feature was obtained through manual inspection. Specifically, for each LOS base station, we cross-checked the approximate orientation and coverage sector using the available data from the EETT registry and mostly through on-site analysis. Due to the lack of complete azimuth and tilt information, this manual approach was necessary to ensure the reliability of the feature. As mentioned earlier, the SectorCoverageFlag feature is relevant and was assessed only under LOS conditions. In our dataset, we found that each measuring spot had LOS conditions with up to three BSs, with very few instances having LOS with more than three BSs. Given this, we applied the SectorCoverageFlag feature only to the first three BSs with LOS conditions. This approach, commonly used in building AI models, involves excluding features that appear in very few instances.

6) BUILT AREA

The number of intersecting buildings between the measurement spot and the 12 closest BSs can serve as a feature for estimating the built area around the spot. To complement this metric with an additional representation of building density, we used QGIS software to calculate the total area covered by buildings within buffer zones of 50m, 75m, and 100m around each measurement location (Fig. 3c). These specific buffer radii were selected based on previous urban studies that have employed similar spatial scales to evaluate the influence of the built environment on spatial parameters [24].

As a second feature, we calculated the average distance from each measurement point to the n closest buildings (Fig. 3d), using n values of 10 and 20. A smaller average distance reflects a more densely built environment surrounding the measurement location. This feature was selected to effectively capture local building density, which is particularly important in the densely built urban environment of Thessaloniki. Distance-based metrics, such as proximity to nearby structures, are commonly used in urban studies to characterize land use and neighborhood form. For instance, Handy et al. [25] emphasized the value of proximity-based indicators in assessing how the built environment shapes spatial behavior and urban structure.

In our study, we experimentally evaluated all combinations of the three buffer sizes and two distance metrics. For this comparison, we used the ExtraTreesRegressor, an ensemble machine learning method (see Section V. Results), while keeping all other input features constant. The best results were obtained using a 50m buffer and the average distance to the 10 closest buildings, which yielded an MAE of 0.3125V/m and an R^2 of 0.7211. In contrast, the other combinations produced MAE values ranging from 0.3152 to 0.3210V/m and R^2 values between 0.7061 and 0.7093. Table 1 provides a summary of the essential features for predicting EMF fields: the first column lists the key features identified from the study of propagation models, the second column presents the corresponding collected features that we were able to estimate based on the available data, the third column shows the feature names and the related values, and the final column identifies the sources and software used to extract the features.

7) IMPLEMENTATION OF THE AI MODELS

After collecting the data for the feature and target variables, the next step was to build and train AI models to predict the electric field values at ground level. Despite the extensive measurement campaign, the dataset of 149 field measurements within an urban environment can be considered relatively small. This was the reason for the special focus on accurate data collection and data cleaning, as described in the paragraphs above.

We employed both ML and DL models, experimenting with different hyperparameter values and tuning to optimize model performance. For DL, we utilized the Keras [26] which is TensorFlow’s high-level API, and for ML, we used the scikit-learn library [27], both implemented in Python. In Table 2 we present the three (3) implementations that produced the best results. As evaluation metrics we report the MAE, RMSE, MAPE and the coefficient of determination, R^2 . The dataset was initially split into a training/validation subset (80%) and a final test subset (20%). Importantly, the final test set remained entirely unused during model training and cross-validation, ensuring an unbiased evaluation of the model’s performance on unseen data. Given the relatively small size of the dataset and the continuous nature of the target variable (electric field strength), a standard random

split could lead to underrepresentation of certain value ranges in the test set. To address this problem, we employed a stratified sampling approach using the StratifiedShuffleSplit method from scikit-learn [28]. The target variable was first discretized into three representative exposure categories — low (0–1.5 V/m), medium (1.5–2.5 V/m), and high (2.5–4.0 V/m) — based on the distribution of the measured values. The StratifiedShuffleSplit technique was then applied to preserve the proportional representation of these categories within the final test set. In other words, the frequency of occurrence of low, medium, and high exposure levels in the test set reflects their distribution in the full dataset. This strategy ensured that the evaluation was balanced across the full range of electric field values and allowed for a more robust assessment of model generalization. To the remaining 80% of the data, we applied 10-fold cross-validation during the model development and hyperparameter tuning phase. In this approach, the training/validation set was divided into 10 equal parts (folds), and the model was trained and validated 10 times, each time using a different fold as the validation set and the remaining nine folds for training. The 10-fold cross-validation is particularly beneficial for small datasets, as it maximizes the use of available data and provides robust performance metrics averaged over multiple iterations. The hyperparameters that yielded the best average results across the folds were then used to retrain the model on the full 80% training/validation set before evaluating it once on the stratified 20% test set.

V. RESULTS

A. PERFORMANCE RESULTS OF AI MODELS

Regarding DL, two implementations provided nearly identical and satisfactory results. The first was a deep learning model implemented using the Keras Functional API (Fig. 4). It processes the input features through locally connected layers, combines these layers, and adds several dense layers for further processing. The locally connected layers included the features (see Table 1): “Distance *x*”, “Height *x*”, “Macrocell *x*”, and “Intersect *x*” for each pair of the twelve BSs and the corresponding spot (Fig. 3a). The locally connected layers are concatenated with the additional features: “SectorCoverageFlag 1”, “SectorCoverageFlag 2”, “SectorCoverageFlag 3”, “Buffer Area”, and “AVG Dist 10 Build”. Subsequently, all features are further processed through fully connected layers (“dense layers”).

The second DL model was implemented using the Keras Sequential API. This model was fully connected, i.e., all inputs (Table 1, Feature Names) were directly applied to every neuron in each subsequent layer. It consisted of three dense layers with 128, 64 and 32 neurons before the single output neuron. Table 2 summarizes the selected hyperparameters of the deep learning models.

Simple ML algorithms did not achieve the performance metrics of the DL models. However, the ExtraTreesRegressor, an ensemble ML method based on random forests, produced very good performance metrics. The model was

configured through a grid search procedure with 10-fold cross-validation on the 80% training/validation set. Several values for the *n_estimators* hyperparameter were tested (50, 100, 150, 200, 250), and 150 estimators were selected as the optimal configuration based on validation performance. Estimators in Extra Trees refer to individual decision trees that are trained on randomly selected subsets of the data and feature subsets, collectively contributing to the ensemble model’s predictions. In the ExtraTreesRegressor used in this study, decision trees were grown without a maximum depth constraint, allowing them to expand fully based on the training data and selected hyperparameters. This model was chosen as it provided superior results in terms of MAE, RMSE and the coefficient of determination (*R*²) comparing to other ML models. The splitting of the dataset and the data preprocessing followed the same approach as the DL models described previously.

TABLE 2. The selected hyperparameters for the two DL implementations.

Hyperparameters	Functional DL model	Sequential DL model
Preprocessing	Standardization (after data splitting)	Standardization (after data splitting)
Layers	Locally + Full connected	Full connected
Hidden Layers	3 (locally connected) + 4 (fully connected)	3
Neurons in Hidden Layers	Locally: 64 each BS, then 64 → 32 Dense: 64 → 32 → 16	128 → 64 → 32
Activation Function	ReLU	ReLU
Regularization	L2 Regularization (0.001) + Dropout (0.2)	L1 Regularization (0.015)
Optimizer	rmsprop (learning rate = 0.0005)	Adam (learning rate = 0.0005)
Loss Function	Mean Squared Error	Mean Squared Error
Metrics	MAE, RMSE, MAPE, R ²	MAE, RMSE, MAPE, R ²
Batch Size	32	32
K-Folds (Train – Test)	10 (on 80% training data for hyperparameter tuning)	10 (on 80% training data for hyperparameter tuning)
Epochs	up to 100	up to 100
Patience (early stopping)	20	10

The results indicate that all three models — the two Deep Learning (DL) approaches and the ExtraTreesRegressor — achieved strong predictive performance on the test set. All models yielded a coefficient of determination (*R*²) around 0.72–0.76, suggesting a high degree of correlation between predicted and actual values and indicating that the models

TABLE 3. Results – metrics of the three DL and ML implementations.

AI methodology	Deep Learning	Deep Learning	Machine learning
Model/Algorithm	Functional, locally connected layers	Sequential model	ExtraTrees Regressor
MAE (V/m)	0.31	0.30	0.31
MAE (dB)	3.60	4.09	3.90
RMSE(V/m)	0.44	0.43	0.46
RMSE (dB)	4.51	5.32	5.04
MAPE (%)	48.7	62.3	55.9
R ²	0.75	0.76	0.72

successfully captured the underlying patterns in the data. The MAE values were very close across all models, ranging from 0.30 to 0.31 V/m, while the RMSE values remained below 0.46 V/m, confirming good overall accuracy in linear scale. When expressed in logarithmic scale (dB), the RMSE ranged from 4.51 to 5.32 dB, with the best performance observed in the Sequential DL model. Although the MAPE metric appears relatively high (48.7% to 62.3%), this is expected given the presence of low electric field values (<1 V/m) in the dataset. In such cases, even minor absolute errors can lead to disproportionately high percentage errors, inflating the MAPE. All three models achieved comparably strong results across the evaluation metrics. Fig. 5 illustrates the performance of the sequential DL model on the test set, showing (a) the predicted versus actual electric field values and (b) the corresponding residuals for each test sample.

The literature suggests that for small datasets, machine learning algorithms—such as the ExtraTrees Regressor—tend to perform well and offer a practical solution [29]. Nonetheless, our deep learning models also delivered competitive results, even with limited data. This indicates that, especially in future studies involving larger datasets, the Functional and Sequential deep learning architectures we implemented could yield even stronger predictive performance.

B. ADJUSTMENT OF PREDICTED ELECTRIC FIELD VALUES ACCORDING TO TIME OF DAY

A significant factor causing fluctuations in the EMF is telecommunication traffic. Previous studies [30] have shown that the electric field is higher during the day, especially during working hours, compared to post-midnight hours. The target values used in this study were obtained from measurements conducted during the late morning to early afternoon (10:00 – 15:00), a time interval with high traffic. To predict EMF for different times of the day, the model needs to be trained with corresponding data, with time as an input for the AI models. A simpler approach is to use data from continuous monitoring sensors in the area of

FIGURE 4. Deep Learning Implementation with Locally Connected Layers. Inputs 1, 2, 3, and 4 to each local layer correspond to the following features: Distance X, Height X, Macrocell X, and Intersect X, as listed in Table 1. The ‘Additional features’ include AVG Dist 10 Build, Buffer Area, and SectorCoverageFlag.

FIGURE 5. (a) Predicted vs. actual electric field values for the sequential deep learning model evaluated on the test set. (b) Corresponding residuals (actual – predicted) across the same test samples.

interest. Continuous radiation monitoring networks record EMF values continuously, allowing their data to be used to assess short-term [30] or long-term variations [31], [32].

1) METHOD

We selected four broadband sensors installed within the specific area (Fig. 1) where spot measurements were conducted. These monitoring sensors are part of the NOEF monitoring network in Greece, which incorporates 500 sensors across the country [33]. The sensors record RMS electric field values every six minutes. The type of sensors used is the AMB-8057-03/G from Narda Safety Test Solutions (Pfullingen, Germany), which records the electric field in the following frequency ranges: a broadband range of 100 kHz – 7 GHz, and three subbands: EGSM 900 Bandpass 925 MHz – 960 MHz, EGSM 1800 Bandpass 1805 MHz – 1880 MHz, and UMTS Bandpass 2110 MHz – 2170 MHz. The network data can provide valuable insights into the behavior, fluctuations, and penetration of different cellular technologies in the EMF environment [34]. We extracted data for the dates corresponding to the measurement periods and collected the electric field values using the broadband filter. Initially, we calculated the mean value per hour for each sensor (E_{hour}). This involved averaging the values recorded for each hour across all days of the collected data. Next, we identified the hour of the day with the highest average value (E_{max}) for each sensor. Subsequently, we computed the next metric for each hour:

$$\text{Percentage to the max} = \frac{E_{hour}}{E_{max}} \cdot 100\% \quad (7)$$

This metric provided the percentage comparison of each hour’s average value relative to the maximum hour’s average value. Fig. 6 shows the average percentage per hour compared to the maximum across all sensors and days. The figure does not show any hour reaching 100% because the different sensors registered their maximum electric field values at slightly different hours. This variability is inherent due to local conditions affecting each sensor differently. Notably, the figure illustrates that after midnight, the electric field is lower. This finding is consistent with previous studies and is attributed to reduced EMF values from cellular networks during periods of lower demand [30], [35].

Our measurements took place between 10:00 and 15:00. We observed that the highest values occur between 17:00 and 22:00. The EMF field during the 10:00 to 15:00 interval, when measurements were performed, shows values close to those observed during the peak evening hours.

The plot in Fig. 6 can be used to apply a correction factor for predicting electric field values at times outside the measurement period. The hourly variation pattern shown in Fig. 6 aligns with the results reported in [35], where long-term monitoring data from the EMF RATEL network also demonstrated similar time-of-day trends in EMF levels. Since electric field values fluctuate throughout the day, the plot shows the percentage of each hour relative to the hour with the maximum value. For instance, late-night measurements typically range from 65% to 75% of the maximum. Therefore, corrections can be applied when predicting electric field values at different times, as the

original measurements were taken during periods of higher telecommunication traffic.

VI. DISCUSSION

In the following section, we compare our work and results on EMF prediction with other related studies, although significant differences exist in data collection methods, frequency bands, and the various environments in which measurements were conducted, including indoor, outdoor, and simulation-based setups. These differences rendered the comparison very difficult to impossible, in some cases. Next, we highlight the three works most similar to ours, although they used data collected through drive test measurements, whereas we conducted spot measurements.

FIGURE 6. Average percentage per hour relative to the maximum value observed in any hour.

In the work by Wang et al. [12], the models achieved Mean Squared Error (MSE) values ranging from 0.000805 to 0.00148 and R^2 scores between 0.665 and 0.813 across two different artificial neural network (ANN) models for predicting EMF exposure using drive test data. All the target electric field values were below 0.8V/m. The collected features included information related to distances to N neighboring base stations (BS), receiver location and time variation. The models were tested with different numbers of neighboring base stations (BSs), specifically using 3, 5, and 7 BSs. The results showed that increasing the number of BSs improved the performance metrics, with better MSE and R^2 values when using more BSs, though the improvement was marginal beyond 5 BSs.

The work by Wang and Wiert [13] achieved R^2 scores between 0.72 and 0.87. In this work, features collected for predicting EMF exposure included the distance to the nearest base stations, receiver location, azimuth of antennas, and time of measurements. Additionally, data from sensor networks and the distance to the nearest sensor were used to enhance predictions in some scenarios. The time of day was incorporated as an input feature to account for daily variations in electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure.

Chikha et al. [15] used moving average techniques to reduce noise in their drive test data. Their model achieved an RMSE of 0.33 V/m. Features collected for predicting RF-EMF exposure included geographical coordinates (X, Y), measurement time, surrounding building density, height and distance to the closest building, and data on the number of active bands and antennas, as well as the distance and average height of active antennas from the 16 closest sites.

Compared to the previous three works, our study has the advantage of using direct measurements at specific spots, which allowed us to collect straightforward electric field values that can be directly compared to the ICNIRP limits. However, a limitation is the smaller number of collected measurements, as drive test measurements are much more time-efficient to gather than spot measurements. Regarding the metrics of the AI models, our results (Table 2) are slightly lower but comparable to those of the previous works. Additionally, while the results of [12] and [13] are noteworthy, the use of random splitting for training and testing datasets with consecutive measurements may have resulted in overoptimistic performance metrics, as this approach can result in training and test sets that share similar spatial characteristics, limiting the ability to accurately assess model generalization [36].

All three previous works, as well as our study, collected features related to the spatial location of the measurements and their distances to BSs. Each study also collected features related to BS/ antenna characteristics. However, due to the limited availability of complete technical specifications for all BSs, different studies included varying BS characteristics. Our work also considers LOS and NLOS conditions, as well as the number of sector antennas from BSs whose half-power beamwidth (HPBW) covers the measurement spot.

The works by [12] and [13] incorporate time as an input feature in their models, since it is known that electric field in the environment varies within a day. In our study, we provide a new approach to predict electric fields at a specific location and on a specific time of the day by leveraging real measurements from continuous monitoring sensors and our proposed predictive model. Continuous monitoring sensors in the area of interest can be used to augment the EMF dataset [13] or assist in assessing EMF variations throughout the day. We propose to transform the electric field values measured at different times of the day to values at the same time of the day (e.g., the time of maximum telecommunication traffic) and use the resulting data to build the model for spatial prediction. Alternatively, as explained above, the electric field can be measured at times of very little variability (e.g., from 10:00 to 15:00, Fig. 6), then be used to create a spatial predictive model, and transformed according to Fig. 6 to predict the field at the same spot but at a different time of the day. However, in the present study neither of the two approaches was validated to evaluate their accuracy.

One of the major highlights of this work is the use of real measurement data, making it the first to predict EMF

values from all downlink cellular frequencies at specific outdoor locations. The input data were carefully validated and corrected, ensuring the reliability of the features used in the prediction models. Additionally, the use of QGIS for determining the number of intersected buildings and assessing the built area around the spot introduced a useful approach for evaluating LOS conditions and analyzing the built environment, a key factor influencing electromagnetic wave propagation and electric field predictions. After applying machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models, solid performance metrics were obtained, indicating that the data features and models selected are appropriate for accurate EMF prediction. One limitation of our work is the lack of direct antenna power and gain data, with only macrocell or microcell classifications available. Access to this information could improve the accuracy of the predictions. Additionally, the absence of direct azimuth, elevation angle, and half-power beamwidth (HPBW) data necessitated the manual assessment of the SectorCoverageFlag feature in the case of LOS conditions with the measurement spot. While this manual approach was effective, automating the process by incorporating these antenna characteristics would significantly reduce the time required, particularly for large datasets with numerous measurements. Moreover, integrating detailed antenna information would enhance the general applicability and scalability of the proposed method across different scenarios and measurement campaigns, enabling broader adoption in practical EMF assessment applications.

VII. CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that predicting electric field values at specific locations is feasible and, under specific circumstances, can be accurate. Key prerequisites include a sufficient number of measurements in the area of interest to train the model and the collection of accurate data for feature variables affecting the measurement at each spot. These data should encompass information about locations, technical specifications of BSs, and features assessing the built environment around each spot. The use of GIS software proves invaluable for collecting such comprehensive data.

Future research should investigate whether models trained in one area (e.g., a dense urban environment, as in our case) can reliably predict electric field values in other areas (e.g., suburban environments) and assess their accuracy. Adopting a more generic approach could potentially enhance the ability to make predictions across different environments without the need for extensive measurement campaigns to assess public exposure to EMF.

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